

Effectiveness of Spill Management Programme on knowledge and practices among health care workers working in selected urban health centers of city

Ms. Sujata Jadhav¹, Mr. Dhiraj Salve²

1. M.Sc. Nursing, Community Health Nursing, Sinhgad College of Nursing, Pune.

2. Lecturer, Sinhgad College of Nursing, Pune.

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ABSTRACT

Background:

Spill management in healthcare settings is a critical component of infection prevention and occupational safety. Inadequate handling of blood and body fluid spills exposes healthcare workers to serious health risks, including transmission of infectious diseases. Despite established protocols, gaps in knowledge and practices persist among healthcare personnel, necessitating structured educational interventions.

AIM:

To evaluate the effectiveness of a Spill Management Programme on the knowledge and practices of healthcare workers working in selected urban health centers.

METHODS:

A quantitative pre-experimental one-group pretest–posttest design was adopted. The study was conducted among 60 healthcare workers selected through non-probability convenient sampling from urban health centers. Data were collected using a self-structured knowledge questionnaire and a modified observational checklist for practices. Following the pretest, a structured Spill Management Programme was administered. Posttest assessment was conducted after 7 days. Data were analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics, including paired t-test and Fisher's exact test.

RESULTS:

Pre-intervention findings indicated that the majority of participants had average knowledge (65%) and poor to average practices (91.7%). Post-intervention results demonstrated significant improvement, with 71.7% of participants achieving good knowledge and 68.3% demonstrating good practices. The mean knowledge score increased from 8.9 to 15.2 ($t = 26.3, p < 0.05$), and the mean practice score improved from 5 to 9.3 ($t = 20.5, p < 0.05$). No significant association was found between demographic variables and knowledge or practice levels.

CONCLUSION:

The Spill Management Programme was found to be highly effective in improving both knowledge and practices among healthcare workers. Structured training interventions can significantly enhance preparedness and reduce occupational risks associated with hazardous spills in healthcare settings.

KEYWORDS:

Spill Management Programme, Healthcare Workers, Knowledge, Practices, Infection Control.

INTRODUCTION

A spill of any hazardous substance on your site can pollute the environment if it is not dealt with properly. A spill outdoors may run straight into the storm water system and pollute the nearest stream, river, beach or groundwater - unless you know what to do and do it immediately¹.

In a hospital, hazardous substances such as body fluids, drugs, cleaning fluids and other chemicals are in very close proximity to hundreds of people each day. Thus, in hospital spillage of blood, body fluids or chemicals can occur at any time due to broken or faulty equipment or human error. Any such spill poses risk to the staff, visitors and patients who are extremely susceptible to infection.²

Blood spills or other human body fluids that occur inside or in the outside environment need to be decontaminated to prevent the potential transmission of communicable disease. The circumstances associated with blood spills can obviously vary greatly depending on the volume and type of contact surface. A small amount of blood, if splashed, can cover a large surface area. A large volume, if undisturbed on a flat surface, can pool in a relatively small area. Because of the unpredictable nature of spills and the various volumes.³

BACKGROUND OF THE STUDY

Spills form an integral part of Bio-Medical Waste (BMW) Management and are addressed under the Bio-Medical Waste (Management and Handling) Rules, 1998 of India, which provide a regulatory framework for the safe handling, segregation, treatment, and disposal of biomedical waste. According to these rules, "bio-medical waste" is defined as any waste that is generated during the diagnosis, treatment, or immunization of human beings or animals, as well as waste produced through research activities related to these processes or during the production and testing of biological materials. Such waste may include blood and body fluids, laboratory specimens, cultures, sharps, discarded medicines, and other contaminated materials. Spills involving biomedical waste are therefore considered potentially hazardous events, as they can lead to the release of infectious agents, toxic substances, or other harmful materials into the hospital environment. If not managed properly, these spills can pose serious risks to healthcare workers, patients, waste handlers, and the surrounding community, including the spread of infections and environmental contamination. The BMW rules emphasize the importance of immediate spill containment, appropriate use of personal protective equipment, proper disinfection, and safe disposal methods to minimize these risks. Incorporating spill management into biomedical waste handling protocols ensures compliance with legal requirements, promotes infection control, and reinforces a culture of safety within healthcare facilities. Effective spill management under the BMW framework not only protects human health but also supports environmental sustainability by preventing the improper release of hazardous waste into air, water, and soil.⁴

NEED OF THE STUDY

Despite significant leaps and advancements in the medical field, issues such as occupational exposure to blood and body fluids continue to pose a major and persistent challenge, with no completely effective means of control. Healthcare workers remain vulnerable to such exposures due to the nature of their work, which involves frequent contact with patients, invasive procedures, and handling of potentially infectious materials. Among all healthcare professionals, nurses form the largest and most essential task force within hospitals, providing continuous bedside care and performing a wide range of clinical tasks. As a result, they are at a particularly high risk of occupational exposure to blood and body fluids on a daily basis.⁵

Blood and body fluid spillage continues to be a major worldwide public health problem, despite substantial advances in the understanding, prevention, and control of infectious diseases. Healthcare settings remain particularly vulnerable to such incidents due to the high frequency of invasive procedures, emergency interventions, and constant contact with patients, all of which increase the risk of exposure to potentially infectious materials. Blood and body fluid spills are known to be potential sources for the transmission of serious blood-borne infections such as hepatitis B, hepatitis C, and human immunodeficiency virus (HIV), thereby posing significant occupational hazards to healthcare workers and safety risks to patients.⁶

METHOD:

Study Design: A Pre-experimental design [one-group pre-test post-test design].

Research approach: The research methodology adopted for the study employed a Quantitative research approach.

Setting: Selected urban health centres of the city.

Sampling technique: Non-probability convenient sampling technique.

Population: Health care workers working in selected urban health centers of city.

Study Protocol: Before the data collection, consent was taken from the participants. The pre-test was conducted before the implementation of the intervention (Spill management programme). Post-test will be conducted after a 7-day gap of intervention to assess the knowledge and practices of spill management.

Data collection

Section I: Description of personal characteristics (Demographic Data)

Section II: To assess the pre-existing knowledge of spill management among health care workers working in selected urban health centers of city.

Section III: To assess the pre-existing practices of spill management among health care workers working in selected urban health centers of city. 47

Section IV: To assess the effectiveness of Spill Management Programme on Knowledge among health care workers working in selected urban health centers of city.

Section V: To assess the effectiveness of Spill Management Programme on practices among health care workers working in selected urban health centers of city.

Section VI: To find out the association of study findings with selected demographical variables.

Method of Data Collection

1. Approval from the research committee members and written permission from head of institution to conduct research.
2. The formal permission for data collection was obtained from municipal corporation and medical officers of urban health centers.
3. The samples of 60 health care workers.
4. Explain the purpose of the research to the participants.
5. Obtain informed consent (written) from the participants.
6. Collect the socio-demographic information
7. Assess the pre-existing knowledge regarding spill management by using structured knowledge questionnaire.
8. Assess the pre-existing practices of spill management by using observational checklist
9. After pre-test spill management programme will be given to experimental group
10. Spill management programme given by using lecture cum discussion and demonstration method through the power-point and video presentation including the introduction, definition, purpose, classification, spill control and prevention, step of management of spill.
11. Post-test will be conducted after a gap of 7 days for experimental group to assess the knowledge and practices of spill management.

Statistical Methods

Descriptive Statistics: Frequency and percentage distribution were used to describe demographic variables. Mean and standard deviation were used to analyse the pre-test and post-test.

Inferential statistics: Paired t-test for the effectiveness of Spill Management Programme on Knowledge and practices among health care workers working in selected urban health centers of city. Fisher's exact test for the association of knowledge and practices regarding spill management among healthcare workers with selected demographical variables.

Data Analysis:

Sample size: For this study, sample size consisted of approximately 60 participants.

Eligibility criteria:

Inclusion criteria

1. Health care workers with a minimum of 6 months of experience.
2. Working in selected urban health centers of city.
3. Willing to participate in the study.

Exclusion criteria

1. Health care workers with less than 6 months of experience.
2. Health care workers not willing to participate in the study.
3. Health care workers who already received the training.

Withdrawal criteria

1. Samples can withdraw from research at any point of time during data collection

RESULTS:

Section I: Description of sample based on their demographic data.

1.1 Age: The percentage-wise distribution of the health care workers according to their age reveals that the respondents were spread across three age groups. The highest percentages (48.3%) of health care workers were in the age group of 31 – 40 years, followed by (36.7%) in the 20 – 30 years age group, and (15.0%) in the 41 - 50 years age group.

1.2 Gender: The percentage-wise distribution of the health care workers according to their gender reveals that the respondents were spread across two genders. The highest percentages (65.0%) of health care workers were the 39 female and the (35.0%) of health care workers were the 21 male.

1.3 Qualification: The percentage-wise distribution of the health care workers according to their qualification reveals that the respondents were spread across according to their Qualification. The highest percentages (40.0%) of health care workers (29) were completed GNM, followed by (25.0%) of health care workers (15) were completed PB B.Sc nursing, (25.0%) of health care workers (15) were completed M.Sc. Nursing, (10.0%) of health care workers (6) were completed B. Sc Nursing.

1.4 Years of experience: The percentage-wise distribution of the health care workers according to their Years of experience reveals that the health care workers were spread across according to their working experience. (33.3%) 20 health care workers had 0-5 years of experience, (36.7%) 22 of them had experience 6-10 years, (20.0%) 12 of them had 11-15 years of experience and (10%) 6 of them had more than 15 years of experience.

1.5 Designation: The percentage-wise distribution of respondents of the health care workers according to their designation reveals that the health care workers were spread across according to their designation. 40% of them were 24 staff nurses, 31.7% of them were 19 senior staff nurses, 21.7% of them were 13 nursing incharge and 6.7% of them were 4 nurse educators.

1.6 Previous training: The percentage-wise distribution of respondents of the health care workers according to their previous training reveals that the health care workers were spread across according to the previous training they were receive or not. (61.7%) 37 health care workers had previous training. And (38.3%) 23 of them had no previous training.

Table No 1: Description of samples (health care workers) based on their personal characteristics in terms of frequency and percentage**(n=60)**

Demographic variable	Freq	%
Age		
20 – 30 years	22	36.7%
31 – 40 years	29	48.3%
41 - 50 years	9	15.0%
Gender		
Male	21	35.0%
Female	39	65.0%
Qualification		
GNM	24	40.0%
B. Sc nursing	6	10.0%
PB B.Sc nursing	15	25.0%
M.Sc. Nursing	15	25.0%
Years of experience		
0 - 5 years	20	33.3%
6 - 10 years	22	36.7%
11 - 15 years	12	20.0%
More than 15 years	6	10.0%
Designation		
Staff nurse	24	40.0%
Senior staff nurse	19	31.7%
Nurse incharge	13	21.7%
Nurse educator	4	6.7%
Previous training		
Yes	37	61.7%
No	23	38.3%

The table presented above provides an analysis of the demographic data of the sample, covering aspects such as age in years, gender, qualification, years of experience, designation, previous training.

Section II: To assess the pre-existing knowledge of spill management among health care workers working in selected urban health centers of city.

The percentage-wise distribution Pre-existing knowledge of spill management among health care workers working in selected urban health centers of city. In pretest, 26.7% of the 16 health care workers has poor knowledge, 65% of them (39) had average knowledge and 8.3% of them (5) had good knowledge regarding spill management.

Table 2: Pre-existing knowledge of spill management among health care workers working in selected urban health centers of city

n=60

Sr.no.	Knowledge	Pretest	
		Freq	%
1.	Poor	16	26.7%
2.	Average	39	65.0%
3.	Good	5	8.3%

Fig no: 1

Bar diagram showing the percentage-wise distribution of Pre-existing knowledge of spill management among health care workers working in selected urban health centers of city.

Section III: To assess the pre-existing practices of spill management among health care workers working in selected urban health centers of city.

The percentage-wise distribution Pre-existing practices of spill management among health care workers working in selected urban health centers of city. In pretest, 26.7% of the 60 health care workers has poor practices, 65.0% of them (39) had average practices and 8.3% of them (5) had good practices regarding spill management.

Table 3: Pre-existing practices of spill management among health care workers working in selected urban health centers of city

n=60

Sr.no.	Practices	Pretest	
		Freq	%
1.	Poor	28	46.7%
2.	Average	27	45.0%
3.	Good	5	8.3%

Fig no: 2

Bar diagram showing the percentage-wise distribution of Pre-existing practices of spill management among health care workers working in selected urban health centers of city.

Section IV: To assess effectiveness of Spill Management Programme on Knowledge among health care workers working in selected urban health centers of city.

The percentage-wise distribution of Effectiveness of spill management Programme on Knowledge among health care workers working in selected urban health centers of city. In pretest, 26.7% of the health care workers has poor knowledge, 65% of them had average knowledge and 8.3% of them had knowledge regarding spill management. In posttest, 28.3% of the health care workers has average knowledge and 71.7% of them had good knowledge regarding spill management.

paired t-test for the effectiveness of Spill Management Programme on Knowledge management among health care workers working in selected urban health centers of city. Average knowledge score in pretest was 8.9 which increased to 15.2 in posttest. T-value for this test was 26.3 with 59 degrees of freedom. Corresponding p-value was small (less than 0.05), the null hypothesis is rejected. Average knowledge score in posttest was significantly higher than that in pretest. It is evident that the spill management programme was significantly effective in improving the knowledge among health care workers regarding spill management.

Table 4.1: Effectiveness of Spill Management Programme on Knowledge among health care workers working in selected urban health centers of city

n=60

Sr.no.	Knowledge	Pretest		Post-test	
		Freq	%	Freq	%
1.	Poor	16	26.7%	0	0.0%
2.	Average	39	65.0%	17	28.3%
3.	Good	5	8.3%	43	71.7%

Table 4.1

Fig no: 3

Bar diagram showing the percentage-wise distribution of Effectiveness of Spill Management Programme on Knowledge among health care workers working in selected urban health centers of city.

Table 4.2: Paired t-test for the effectiveness of Spill Management Programme on Knowledge among health care workers working in selected urban health centers of city

n=60

Sr.no	Test	Mean	SD	T	df	p-value
1.	Pretest	8.9	3.3	26.3	59	0.000
2.	Posttest	15.2	3.2			

Table 4.2

Fig no: 4.

Bar diagram showing the effectiveness of Spill Management Programme on Knowledge among health care workers working in selected urban health centers of city in pretest and posttest.

Researcher applied paired t-test for the effectiveness of Spill Management Programme on Knowledge management among health care workers working in selected urban health centers of city. Average knowledge score in pretest was 8.9 which increased to 15.2 in posttest. T-value for this test was 26.3 with 59 degrees of freedom. Corresponding p-value was small (less than 0.05), the null hypothesis is rejected. Average knowledge score in posttest was significantly higher than that in pretest. It is evident that the spill management programme was significantly effective in improving the knowledge among health care workers regarding spill management.

Table 4.3: Knowledge item analysis**n=60**

Sr.no	Knowledge	Pretest		Posttest	
		Freq	%	Freq	%
1.	Common hazard in hospitals due to the presence of hazardous substances	38	63.3%	54	90.0%
2.	Cause of spillage of hazardous substances in a hospital	27	45.0%	54	90.0%
3.	Extremely susceptible to infection in case of a spill in a hospital?	27	45.0%	45	75.0%
4.	Spill defined as	30	50.0%	47	78.3%
5.	Spill cause harm to?	27	45.0%	46	76.7%
6.	Primary benefits of effective spill management in a hospital setting	23	38.3%	45	75.0%
7.	Spill management help reduce the risk of accidents?	26	43.3%	45	75.0%
8.	Environmental benefits of effective spill management?	24	40.0%	47	78.3%
9.	Spill management help hospitals financially?	27	45.0%	40	66.7%
10.	What is included in the training for hospital staff on spill management?	19	31.7%	45	75.0%
11.	Purpose of developing a spill management plan?	26	43.3%	46	76.7%
12.	Benefit of training hospital staff on spill management procedures?	27	45.0%	46	76.7%
13.	First step in responding to a spill?	29	48.3%	47	78.3%
14.	Information should be gathered during the assessment of a spill?	30	50.0%	40	66.7%
15.	Personal protective equipment (PPE) may be worn during spill cleanup?	18	30.0%	42	70.0%
16.	Biological spill in a hospital setting?	31	51.7%	40	66.7%
17.	What will used to dispose of debris appropriately after cleaning up a blood spill?	22	36.7%	41	68.3%
18.	Disinfectant concentration is recommended for cleaning up blood spills?	22	36.7%	38	63.3%
19.	Disinfectant allowed to contact the surface for major spills	29	48.3%	55	91.7%
20.	Where should paper towels used to clean up a spill be disposed of	34	56.7%	47	78.3%

Table 4.3

Table presents the frequency and percentage of correct responses by health care workers to each knowledge item. It is clear that the correct responses for each practices item improved remarkably in posttest as compared to that in pretest. This indicates that there is remarkable improvement in the knowledge among health care workers after Spill Management Programme.

Fig no: 5

Bar diagram showing the % correct response by health care workers to each knowledge item in pretest and posttest

Section V: To assess effectiveness of Spill Management Programme on practices among health care workers working in selected urban health centers of city.

In pretest, 46.7% of the health care workers has poor practices, 45% of them had average practices and 8.3% of them had good practices regarding spill management. In posttest, 31.7% of the health care workers had average practices and 68.3% of them had good practices regarding spill management.

paired t-test for the effectiveness of Spill Management Programme on practices among health care workers working in selected urban health centers of city. Average practices score in pretest was 5 which increased to 9.3 in posttest. T-value for this test was 20.5 with 59 degrees of freedom. Corresponding p-value was small (less than 0.05), the null hypothesis is rejected. Average practices score in posttest was significantly higher than that in pretest. It is evident that the spill management programme was significantly effective in improving the practices among health care workers regarding spill management.

Table 5.1: Effectiveness of Spill Management Programme on practices among health care workers working in selected urban health centers of city

n=60

Sr. no.	Practices	Pretest		Posttest	
		Freq	%	Freq	%
1.	Poor	28	46.7%	0	0.0%
2.	Average	27	45.0%	19	31.7%
3.	Good	5	8.3%	41	68.3%

Table 5.1

Fig no: 6

Bar diagram showing the percentage-wise distribution of Effectiveness of Spill Management Programme on practices among health care workers working in selected urban health centers of city.

Table 5.2: Paired t-test for the effectiveness of Spill Management Programme on practices among health care workers working in selected urban health centers of city

n=60

Sr.no	Test	Mean	SD	T	df	p-value
1.	Pretest	5.0	2.2	20.5	59	0.000
2.	Posttest	9.3	1.7			

Table 5.2**Fig no: 7**

Bar diagram showing the effectiveness of Spill Management Programme on practices among health care workers working in selected urban health centers of city in pretest and posttest

Researcher applied paired t-test for the effectiveness of Spill Management Programme on practices among health care workers working in selected urban health centers of city. Average practices score in pretest was 5 which increased to 9.3 in posttest. T-value for this test was 20.5 with 59 degrees of freedom. Corresponding p-value was small (less than 0.05), the null hypothesis is rejected. Average practices score in posttest was significantly higher than that in pretest. It is evident that the spill management programme was significantly effective in improving the practices among health care workers regarding spill management.

Table 5.3: Practices item analysis**n=60**

Sr. no	Practices	Pretest		Posttest	
		Freq	%	Freq	%
1.	Spillage should be attended immediately.	33	55.0%	60	100.0%
2.	Mark the spill area.	22	36.7%	57	95.0%
3.	Entry to the spill area should be restricted to persons who are involved in management.	23	38.3%	49	81.7%
4.	Bring the spill kit containing all material to the site of spillage.	29	48.3%	48	80.0%
5.	Wear appropriate PPE (gloves and gown).	28	46.7%	42	70.0%
6.	Cover the spill with paper towels to absorb the spillage	24	40.0%	44	73.3%
7.	Pour 0.5% sodium hypochlorite (freshly prepared) on top of paper towels and leave it for 15 minutes.	25	41.7%	42	70.0%
8.	After 15 minutes, remove the paper towels; put fresh paper towels to clean the area. Then all these towels are to be discarded as infectious waste. Wipe the area with 0.5% sodium hypochlorite (freshly prepared)	14	23.3%	58	96.7%
9.	Wash the area with soap and water.	41	68.3%	49	81.7%
10.	Remove PPE. All PPE material and paper towel etc. are to be discarded as infectious waste in appropriate waste container.	30	50.0%	44	73.3%
11.	Perform hand hygiene.	26	43.3%	42	70.0%
12.	Record the incident.	7	11.7%	24	40.0%

Table 5.3

Table presents the frequency and percentage of health care workers following each practice item. It is clear that the percentage of compliance for each practice item improved remarkably in posttest as compared to that in pretest. This indicates that there is remarkable improvement in the practices among health care workers after Spill Management Programme.

Fig no: 8

Bar diagram showing the % correct response by health care workers to each practices item in pretest and posttest.

Section VI: To find the association of study findings with selected demographical variables.

Fisher's exact test indicated all the p-values were large (greater than 0.05), none of the demographic variables was found to have significant association with the knowledge and practices among health care workers regarding spill management.

Table 6.1: Fisher's exact test for the association of knowledge regarding spill management among healthcare workers with selected demographical variables

n=60

Sr.no.	Demographic variable		Knowledge			p-value
			Poor	Average	Good	
1.	Age	20 – 30 years	7	13	2	0.933
		31 – 40 years	7	20	2	
		41 - 50 years	2	6	1	
2.	Gender	Male	7	12	2	0.576
		Female	9	27	3	
3.	Qualification	GNM	4	19	1	0.417
		B. Sc nursing	6	8	1	
		PB B.Sc nursing	5	8	2	
		M.Sc. Nursing	1	4	1	
4.	Years of experience	0 - 5 years	4	15	1	0.458
		6 - 10 years	6	15	1	
		11 - 15 years	5	5	2	
		More than 15 years	1	4	1	
5.	Designation	Staff nurse	19	1	4	0.427
		Senior staff nurse	11	2	6	
		Nurse incharge	7	1	5	
		Nurse educator	2	1	1	
6.	Previous training	Yes	10	23	4	0.770
		No	6	16	1	

Since all the p-values were large (greater than 0.05), none of the demographic variables was found to have significant association with the knowledge among health care workers regarding spill management.

Table 6.2: Fisher's exact test for the association of practices regarding spill management among healthcare workers with selected demographical variables**n=60**

Sr.no.	Demographic variable		Practices			p-value
			Poor	Average	Good	
1.	Age	20 – 30 years	8	10	4	0.338
		31 – 40 years	16	12	1	
		41 - 50 years	4	5	0	
2.	Gender	Male	9	10	2	0.923
		Female	19	17	3	
3.	Qualification	GNM	9	11	4	0.561
		B. Sc nursing	8	6	1	
		PB B.Sc nursing	9	6	0	
		M.Sc. Nursing	2	4	0	
4.	Years of experience	0 - 5 years	9	9	2	0.945
		6 - 10 years	10	10	2	
		11 - 15 years	6	6	0	
		More than 15 years	3	2	1	
5.	Designation	Staff nurse	12	3	9	0.826
		Senior staff nurse	8	2	9	
		Nurse in charge	5	0	8	
		Nurse educator	2	0	2	
6.	Previous training	Yes	19	14	4	0.372
		No	9	13	1	

Since all the p-values were large (greater than 0.05), none of the demographic variables was found to have significant association with the practices among health care workers regarding spill management.

RECOMMENDATIONS:

The researcher recommended the following studies

- The same study can be conducted on larger samples for better generalization.
- A similar study can be conducted with two group control and experimental.
- The study can be conducted on individuals rather than groups.
- A similar study could be replicated in different settings.

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